

A didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre: pathways to Global Citizenship in the internationalization context /

Uma sequência didática para o gênero redação do ENEM: caminhos em direção à Cidadania Global no âmbito da internacionalização

*Rodrigo Schaefer**

PhD in English: Linguistic and Literary Studies from the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC, Brazil). Post-doctorate researcher in Linguistics at Humboldt Universität zu Berlin through the CAPES/Humboldt Program. Professor-researcher in the language department (English and Portuguese) from Instituto Federal Catarinense (IFC).

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2349-0175>

Received: December, 8th, 2024. **Approved:** December, 10th, 2024.

How to quote this article:

SCHAEFER, R. A didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre: pathways to Global Citizenship in the internationalization context. *Revista Letras Raras*. Campina Grande, v. 13, n. 5, e5412, dec. 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14562135>

ABSTRACT

The author of this study suggests that Global Citizenship education, which is related to people who care about issues belonging to the local and global sphere (Clifford, 2018), can be facilitated through a didactic sequence which, in turn, aims to contribute to the ENEM textual genre in Brazilian high schools. Thus, drawing on scholars such as Cavalcante and Silva (2023) and Hanna (2024), this study has two objectives: (1) to present a didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre; (2) to promote, through the didactic sequence, Global Citizenship education in the internationalization context. The didactic sequence, which can be applied over the course of 15 classes, encompasses (a) the virtual exchange regarding high school students from a Brazilian school with students from two foreign schools, and (b) the production of digital stories. It can be stated that didactic sequences dealing with the ENEM textual genre, such as the sequence that was presented in this study, can encourage critical thinking in Brazilian schools and foster education for Global Citizenship in the context of internationalization.

KEYWORDS: ENEM Textual Genre; Global Citizenship Education; Internationalization; Digital Stories; Virtual Exchange.

RESUMO

O autor do presente estudo sugere que a educação para a Cidadania Global, relacionada com pessoas que se preocupam com questões pertencentes ao âmbito local e global (Clifford, 2018), pode ser promovida mediante uma sequência didática que, por sua vez, tem como propósito contribuir para o trabalho com o gênero redação do ENEM nas escolas brasileiras de ensino médio. Assim, com base em autores como Cavalcante e Silva (2023) e Hanna

*

 rodrigo.schaefer@ifc.edu.br

(2024), este estudo tem dois objetivos: (1) apresentar uma sugestão de sequência didática para o gênero redação do ENEM; (2) fomentar, por intermédio da sequência didática, a educação para a Cidadania Global no âmbito da internacionalização. A sequência didática, que pode ser aplicada no transcorrer de 15 aulas, abarca (a) o intercâmbio virtual de estudantes do ensino médio de uma escola brasileira com estudantes de duas escolas estrangeiras, e (b) a produção de histórias digitais. Pode-se afirmar que sequências didáticas envolvendo o trabalho com o gênero redação do ENEM, tal como a sequência que neste estudo se erigiu, podem propiciar o pensamento crítico nas escolas brasileiras e o fomento da educação para a Cidadania Global no contexto da internacionalização.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Redação do ENEM; Educação para a Cidadania Global; Internacionalização; Histórias Digitais; Intercâmbio Virtual.

1 Introduction

In 1996, the document *Standards for Foreign Language Learning: Preparing for the 21st Century* was published. It presented “5 Cs” for teaching and learning foreign languages, which were *communication, cultures, connections, comparisons* and *communities*. Essentially, *communication* refers to meaningful communicative experiences, which are in tune with the real purposes of language use, while *cultures* emphasizes the importance of including aspects of a (multi/pluri)cultural nature and of local and global scope in teaching. *Connections*, on the other hand, highlights the interdisciplinary relationship of knowledge, that is, between the different subjects of the school curriculum, and *comparisons*, in turn, points to the need for teachers to provide students with opportunities to compare linguistic and cultural aspects related to different peoples and countries. Finally, *communities* indicates the indispensability of students participating in linguistic communities in their own country as well as in other cultural contexts where the target language is spoken.

As can be seen from the document described above, the inseparability between language and culture(s) was already pointed out, as well as the importance of using themes regarding the local and global spheres in the classroom. In fact, this study, as will be seen below, is consistent with the notion of education for Global Citizenship, but also internationalization in the teaching and learning the Portuguese language context.

According to Hanna (2024), in the face of current social and technological transformations, it is imperative that students, in addition to being aware of the role they play in the world as individuals, understand that we have an influence on the lives of people who are far and near to us. For this reason, the author claims that it is up to educational institutions, through actions that foster their internationalization, to provide students with the means to become citizens of the world,

thus encouraging “a more global mindset”¹ (p. 81). Belli and Luna (2024), in turn, argue that the internationalization of education is a reflection of globalization, considering that the latter “expands the various interfaces that exist between the countries and peoples of the world”² (p. 10). In this connection, Belli and Luna (2024) stress that educational institutions must adapt their policies and theoretical-methodological procedures to the emerging demands of a globalized society.

With regard specifically to the internationalization of Portuguese, Mesquita (2024) explains that this language, spoken in four continents (South America, Asia, Africa and Europe) and with 250 million users, has currently achieved visibility on an international and global level, occupying a prominent place in literary and scientific production and dissemination on social networks and on search engines. In this way, Portuguese is characterized as a *supercentral language*, a term used to designate languages that are widely spoken and that, therefore, foster the contact between speakers of central languages, such as, in addition to Portuguese, French, English and German. In this respect, Becker (2015) had already stated that, due to historical-social changes in the Portuguese language, together with globalization, it is necessary for internationalization strategies to take such changes into account and, at the same time, for institutions to adapt the teaching of Portuguese in line with current social, political and cultural particularities.

The author of this study chose to present a didactic sequence as a strategy for working with the ENEM (National High School Exam³) textual genre with the purpose of promoting education for Global Citizenship and the internationalization of the Portuguese language in high school. The ENEM exam, whose objective is to evaluate the performance of students who are finishing basic schooling, was instituted in 1998 and is promoted annually by National Institute of Studies and Educational Research Anísio Teixeira⁴. In this national Brazilian exam, candidates are asked to write an essay in the argumentative style regarding a theme proposed by ENEM, through which they must present a point of view, or thesis, and defend it by putting forward arguments, citations, historical-scientific facts, political and social data, among other possibilities (Cavalcante; Silva, 2023).

Therefore, this study has two objectives: (1) to present a didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre; (2) to promote, through this didactic sequence, education for Global Citizenship in

¹ Original quote: “uma mentalidade mais global”.

² Original quote: “dilata as diversas interfaces existentes entre os países e os povos do mundo”.

³ This National Entrance Exam for universities in Brazil is named, in Portuguese, *Exame Nacional do Ensino Médio*.

⁴ In Portuguese, *Instituto Nacional de Estudos e Pesquisas Educacionais Anísio Teixeira* (INEP).

the internationalization context. It should be noted that the didactic sequence includes virtual exchange (O'Dowd, 2023a, 2023b; Schaefer, 2022), which, in this study, allows high school students from a Brazilian school to come into contact with students from two foreign schools, and the creation of digital stories (Robin, 2016; Rodgers; Ní Dhonnchadha, 2023; Schaefer, 2022; Schaefer; Heemann, 2024), through which students will be encouraged to reflect on different social themes.

The way in which this study has the potential to contribute to the ENEM textual genre can be explained by three main reasons. First, as stated by Hudzik (2011, p. 22), it is crucial to “move from rhetoric to action” to foster internationalization, which means that there is a need to promote the systematization between theory and practice. The second reason, in turn, converges with Nunes and Silva (2022). The authors draw attention to the fact that language teaching in Brazilian institutions, often conservative and dogmatic, is not committed to activities that encourage students to be part of meaningful linguistic and discursive situations. From this perspective, through the didactic sequence of this work, it is possible to stimulate creativity, intercultural communication and critical thinking. Given the above, it could be stated that this study enables not only internationalization through the didactic sequence, but also education for Global Citizenship.

Finally, the third reason that attests to the relevance of this study refers to the “lack of publications”⁵ (Caparros Junior, 2020, p. 117) regarding research in the context of internationalization, as well as, in line with Britz and Morosini (2023, p. 271), the understanding that “internationalization in the context of Basic Education is little studied and discussed in Brazil”⁶, taking into account that the didactic sequence of this study is aimed at students from the 1st to the 3rd year of high school.

This text is divided into five sections. The first section concentrated on the objective, as well as a brief contextualization concerning this study. The second and third sections, for its part, will address theoretical contributions on education for Global Citizenship, internationalization, ENEM textual genre, didactic sequence, virtual exchange and digital stories. Then, in the fourth section, the focus will be on the presentation of the didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre and, lastly, some final considerations will be made.

2 Education for Global Citizenship and internationalization

⁵ Original quote: “carência de publicações”.

⁶ Original quote: “a internacionalização no âmbito da Educação Básica é pouco estudada e discutida no Brasil”.

For Hanna (2024), in industrial society, the focus of teaching and learning was the construction of procedural and factual knowledge. However, in the information and knowledge society, due to the “imperative force of internationalization, interculturality, and global citizenship”⁷ (Hanna, 2024, p. 91), there is an urgent need to develop meta-cognitive skills, including critical thinking and the evaluation of arguments and information in general.

Clifford (2018) relates the concept of Global Citizenship to people who are concerned with issues pertaining to the local, international and global spheres, while at the same time “understand that the world is interdependent, that every action we take, every decision we make, affects other people” (p. 15). Similarly, Belli and Luna (2024) argue that education for Global Citizenship needs to be aware of the global transformations that have occurred over the centuries. Thus, “education can be global, as well as multicultural and multilingual. Education can become international. This is a challenge”⁸ (Belli; Luna, 2024, p. 10). To this end, it is essential that educational practices are articulated with issues involving the local, regional and global spheres.

The document published by UNESCO in 2015, entitled *Global Citizenship Education: Topics and Learning Objectives*, discusses three elements deemed to be essential to make students global citizens, which converges with the need for education for Global Citizenship previously highlighted by Hanna (2024) and Belli and Luna (2024). The first of these elements, *cognitive*, is associated with the relevance of students developing critical thinking skills based on the analysis of documents, texts, videos, etc.; *socio-emotional*, the second element, points to empathy and respect as characteristics necessary for cultural diversity; finally, *behavioral*, is consistent with the importance of instilling in students the interest in implementing actions aimed at solving social problems.

Belli and Luna (2024) underline that educational practices and actions for internationalization are materialized from the school curriculum, which is considered “the school’s identity document”⁹ (p. 10). For the authors, who argue that curricular internationalization “seeks to transform students into global citizens with social responsibility, respect for differences and

⁷ Original quote: “imperiosa força da internacionalização, da interculturalidade, da cidadania global”.

⁸ Original quote: “a educação pode ser global, além de multicultural e multilíngue. A educação pode internacionalizar-se. Trata-se de um desafio”.

⁹ Original quote: “o documento de identidade da escola”.

intercultural communicability”¹⁰ (Belli; Luna, 2024, p. 23), “the marks of the internationalization of HEIs¹¹ are perceived and registered, formally or not”¹² (p. 10), through the activities and content present in the curriculum.

According to Leask (2015), the internationalization of the curriculum concerns the implementation of intercultural, global and international dimensions in curriculum activities. In this context, the study of languages is viewed as a possibility for transforming social relations, allowing “the construction of a more just and democratic society that cares about global problems”¹³ (Guimarães; Silva, 2022, p. 42), while, in line with what Becker (2015) highlighted in the introductory section of this work, it is necessary, for the purposes of internationalizing Portuguese, that teaching strategies pay attention to social, political and cultural aspects related to the language in different parts of the world. It should be stressed that the didactic sequence of this study facilitates the contact of students from a Brazilian school with students from two foreign schools, namely, one from East Timor and the other from Germany, an opportunity that, as will be seen later, is committed to critical thinking and education for Global Citizenship.

In East Timor, according to the website¹⁴ of the University of International Integration of Afro-Brazilian Lusophony¹⁵, Portuguese, considered the official language in that country, is spoken by almost 20% of the population, especially by the elderly, and the most widely spoken language is Tetum. For Severo and Leviski (2019), who argue that teaching Portuguese can foster the internationalization of the language, addressing the linguistic and cultural characteristics of countries where Portuguese is an official language, including East Timor, Angola, Guinea-Bissau and Cape Verde, can contribute to the recognition of the pluricentrism of the Portuguese language, e.g. the varieties of Portuguese emerging in East Timor and in African countries. In German educational institutions, for their part, one of the understandings that underlines the relevance of Portuguese as an additional language, as well as didactic proposals for teaching this language, lies in the fact that “German foreign trade with this country [Brazil] represents about a third of the total

¹⁰ Original quote: “busca transformar os estudantes em cidadãos globais com responsabilidade social, respeito ao diferente e comunicabilidade intercultural”.

¹¹ Higher Education Institutions.

¹² Original quote: “as marcas da internacionalização das IES são percebidas e registradas, formalmente ou não”.

¹³ Original quote: “a construção de uma sociedade mais justa e democrática e que se importa com os problemas de cunho global”.

¹⁴ Link to access the website: <https://unilab.edu.br/2012/03/26/conheca-mais-o-timor-leste/>

¹⁵ *Universidade da Integração Internacional da Lusofonia Afro-Brasileira.*

volume of German foreign trade with Latin America”¹⁶ (Reimann, 2022, p. 259). Despite this, Reimann (2022) stresses that, in the German education system, Portuguese has not received enough attention.

The author of this study suggests that both education for Global Citizenship and internationalization can be fostered by a didactic sequence that, made possible through the use of digital technologies, aims to contribute to the ENEM textual genre in Brazilian high schools.

It is possible to state that the use of digital tools in the context of teaching and learning Portuguese has the potential to provide a pluricentric view of the language, a perspective that is characterized by the fact that pluricentric languages have more than one center of reference (Miguel, 2022). According to Miguel (2022), these tools enable social interaction, communication, and interpersonal contact. In view of this, “A pluricentric perspective of Portuguese, combined with digital technologies, appears to be the key to the perennial vitality and radiant future of the Portuguese language”¹⁷ (Miguel, 2022, p. 56). For such a perspective to materialize, Miguel (2022) argues that further research is needed, such as the didactic sequence of this article, which encompasses, as already mentioned, the use of digital tools. Bearing in mind Miguel's (2022) considerations, there is the possibility that, through the didactic sequence of this study, not only learning related to the ENEM textual genre can be facilitated, but also creativity, intercultural communication, the pluricentric vision of Portuguese, and the critical thinking of students.

Next, some theories related not only to the ENEM textual genre and didactic sequence will be addressed, but also virtual exchange and digital stories, given that the didactic sequence of this study comprises online intercultural contact and the creation of stories through the use of different digital resources.

3 The ENEM textual genre, didactic sequence, virtual exchange and digital stories

As mentioned in the Introduction session, in the ENEM exam, candidates are asked to write an essay in the argumentative style according to a specific theme. In this essay, as Cavalcante and Silva (2023) explain, they must present a point of view, or thesis, and defend it by introducing

¹⁶ Original quote: “o comércio exterior alemão com este país [Brasil] representa cerca de um terço do volume total do comércio alemão exterior com a América latina”.

¹⁷ Original quote: “Uma perspectiva pluricêntrica do português, aliada às tecnologias digitais, afigura-se como chave para a vitalidade perene e futuro radioso da língua portuguesa”.

quotations, political and social data, arguments, historical-scientific facts, among other possibilities. In addition, candidates must draw up a proposal for social intervention to solve the problem addressed or, at the very least, to mitigate it. Interestingly, due to the peculiarities in question, Cavalcante and Silva (2023, p. 51) use the term “ENEM textual genre”¹⁸, which will also be adopted in this study, to refer to the essay required by ENEM, in the sense that, given its peculiar features, it is characterized “as a discourse genre”¹⁹ (Cavalcante; Silva, 2023, p. 53).

The author of this study selected a didactic sequence as a facilitating strategy for students to familiarize themselves with the structure, writing and characteristics concerning the ENEM textual genre, as well as to promote education for Global Citizenship and the internationalization of the Portuguese language.

For Zabala (1998, p. 18), didactic sequence can be defined as “A set of ordered, structured and articulated activities for the achievement of certain educational objectives, which have a beginning and an end known to both teachers and students”²⁰. Consequently, the author emphasizes that didactic sequences must be adapted based on the established objectives as well as on the curricular content.

Costa-Hübes and Simioni (2014) and Cabral (2017) make clear that a didactic sequence is made up of elements ordered in a lesson proposal. Traditionally, it entails the presentation of the content to be taught, its subsequent studies and/or exercises and, lastly, evaluation procedures (Zabala, 2018). Zabala (1998), Costa-Hübes and Simioni (2014) and Cabral (2017) add that a didactic sequence can be based on different theoretical assumptions. It should be stressed that the didactic sequence of this work is based on theories arising, above all, from the area of internationalization and education for Global Citizenship.

As previously stated, the didactic sequence of this study, which will be presented in the next section, comprises virtual exchange and the production of digital stories. According to Schaefer and Heemann (2024), virtual exchange and digital stories, which are made possible by digital technologies, have the potential to foster internationalization and education for Global Citizenship.

¹⁸ In Portuguese, *gênero redação do ENEM*.

¹⁹ Original quote: “como um gênero do discurso”.

²⁰ Original quote: “Um conjunto de atividades ordenadas, estruturadas e articuladas para a realização de certos objetivos educacionais, que têm um princípio e um fim conhecidos tanto pelos professores como pelos alunos”.

For O'Dowd (2019), through virtual exchange, which has come to the fore in the context of teaching and learning additional languages in recent decades, groups of students interact with students from other countries over a period of time. Similarly, O'Dowd (2023a, 2023b) makes clear that online interaction between students from different cultures has received special attention from educational institutions whose aim is to provide students with a meaningful language learning experience. Following this line of thought, Schaefer *et al.* (2017, p. 239) argue that virtual exchange is “an instrument for connecting with the world, capable of promoting intercultural encounters between students”²¹.

The creation of digital stories, which allows students of Portuguese to tell stories using a variety of digital resources such as images, music and recorded narration (Robin, 2016; Rodgers; Ní Dhonnchadha, 2023; Schaefer, 2022; Schaefer; Heemann, 2024), contributes to the development of students' critical thinking (Robin, 2016; Schaefer; Heemann, 2024), since they “begin to research and tell stories of their own [as well as] to research rich, deep content while analyzing and synthesizing a wide range of information and opinions” (Robin, 2016, p. 19).

Lambert (2006, 2007) suggests that digital storytelling has seven elements, namely: 1) point of view, 2) dramatic question, 3) emotional content, 4) the gift of voice, 5) the power of the soundtrack, 6) economy of language and 7) pacing. The first element, *point of view*, refers to the central topic of a story, since stories, in general, contribute to the presentation of a variety of ideas. *Dramatic question*, in turn, concerns a question posed by the student that has the potential to attract the audience's attention. *Emotional content*, the third element, evokes emotional connections with, among other possibilities, love, illness, graduation, death, sense of loneliness, acceptance and rejection. While *the gift of voice* has to do with the use of the narrator's voice, which helps to highlight the emotional content, *the power of the soundtrack*, the fifth element, adds an emotional tone to the story, as soundtracks “change the way we perceive the visual information streaming into our eyes, and establish a rhythm” (Lambert, 2006, p. 55). *Economy of language* means that the narration should only provide the content that is crucial for the understanding of the story. Lastly, *pacing* is related to the fact that the story should not be narrated either too fast or too slowly, so that the audience can clearly understand its content.

For Lambert (2006, 2007), the production of digital stories requires several steps. *Planning* involves establishing all the procedures that make up the creation of a digital story; *presenting*

²¹ Original quote: “um instrumento de ligação com o mundo, capaz de promover encontros interculturais entre estudantes”.

samples refers to the need to provide students with examples of digital stories previously created by others. While *scripting* refers to the writing of the events that comprise the story itself, *receiving feedback* encompasses the linguistic correction of the script, which can be provided by the teacher or by peers. *Designing storyboard* refers to the illustrations that represent the story's script as a whole, followed by the *digitization of the story*, that is, the inclusion of digital elements, such as images, script narration and background music, in the stories. Finally, *presentation to an audience* allows students to share their stories.

The study by Rodgers and Ní Dhonnchadha (2023), which investigated the production of digital stories with biotechnology and additional language students, aimed to discuss the extent to which the stories facilitated the learning of linguistic and grammatical features. More specifically, the students created digital stories based on forensic cases in which DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid) profiling was used. The outcomes of the research showed the contribution of digital stories in relation to specialized language skills, in this case in the area of Biotechnology. Although Rodgers and Ní Dhonnchadha (2023) emphasize the beneficial aspects of digital stories for today's globalized world, the results, which revealed mainly linguistic and academic contributions, did not address to what extent, specifically, the stories served as a promoter of Global Citizenship education. In fact, my study aims to introduce the potential of stories for learning Portuguese as a mother tongue (students from Brazil who are Portuguese speakers) as well as additional language, but also for Global Citizenship.

Castañeda's (2013) study, on the other hand, based on narratives, aimed to analyze, through the creation of stories in additional language classes, the effects related to the learners' participation in the production of these stories. To collect data, the author included questionnaires, focus groups, interviews and reflective diaries by the researcher. The results, which are consistent with Robin's (2016) view that digital stories provide full student involvement, revealed that the learners "practiced language in an expressive manner and engaged in real-world communication" (Castañeda, p. 56).

In view of what was previously explained about Global Citizenship, internationalization, the ENEM textual genre, didactic sequence, virtual exchange and digital stories, in the following section a didactic sequence will be presented for the genre at issue.

4 A didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre: pathways to Global Citizenship

4.1 Some opening remarks

Before presenting the didactic sequence, it is worth highlighting a few considerations. Firstly, it encompasses, as already mentioned, digital storytelling and virtual exchange. Secondly, it provides intercultural contact between high school students from a Brazilian school (BS) and students from two foreign institutions, specifically a Timorese secondary school²² (TS) and a German school²³ (GS) which offers Portuguese teaching from intermediate level.

The choice of a TS and a GS to establish a partnership with a Brazilian school (BS) can be justified (a) by the fact that Portuguese is an official language in both Brazil and East Timor and, in the case of Germany, as already explained, Portuguese as an additional language has not been the subject of sufficient attention (Becker, 2015; Reimann, 2022); (b) by the possibility of exploring linguistic-cultural differences related to Brazil and East Timor; (c) by the opportunity to make available the contact with students from Germany who are learning Portuguese as an additional language.

As mentioned earlier, the website University of International Integration of Afro-Brazilian Lusophony explains that Portuguese is spoken by approximately 20% of the Timorese population, most of whom are elderly. In fact, despite the fact that many young people in East Timor are against the need to study the Portuguese language, which they perceive as a *colonial language*, in reference to the colonization processes once undertaken by Portugal, Portuguese Prime Minister António Costa stressed, according to a news item published on the *Socialist Party*²⁴ website²⁵ in 2023, the importance of teaching this language in East Timorese territory, as it “reinforces East Timor’s identity, makes East Timor’s identity”²⁶ (PS). In addition, in line with Leiria (2010, p. 12), Portuguese is “the vehicular language for accessing the knowledge of other subjects”²⁷ in the school curriculum. On that basis, this didactic sequence is also committed to the task of helping Timorese students to consolidate their language skills.

²² According to the Portuguese Program for Secondary Schools (*Programa de Português para as Escolas de Ensino Secundário*), Portuguese, “not being the mother tongue of most Timorese students, assumes a peculiar status in East Timor, specifically in the Timorese school context, constituting one of the official and schooling languages (alongside Tetum)” (TIMOR-LESTE, 2011, p. 4). Original quote: “não sendo língua materna da maioria dos alunos timorenses, assume um estatuto peculiar em Timor-Leste, especificamente no contexto escolar timorense, constituindo-se como uma das línguas oficiais e de escolarização (a par do Tétum)”.

²³ Below are four suggestions for institutions according to Reimann (2022).

²⁴ In Portuguese, *PS* (*Partido Socialista*).

²⁵ Link to access the website: <https://ps.pt/antonio-costa-lingua-portuguesa-faz-a-identidade-de-timor-leste/>

²⁶ Original quote: “reforça a identidade de Timor-Leste, faz a identidade de Timor-Leste”.

²⁷ Original quote: “a língua veicular de acesso aos conhecimentos de outras disciplinas”.

In the section that discussed the theoretical framework of this work, it was explained that, in Germany, Portuguese teaching lacks didactic teaching proposals, in order to improve the quality of classes in German institutions (Reimann, 2022). It is suggested that, given the nature of the activities that make up the didactic sequence of this work, groups of GS students who have prior knowledge of Portuguese be selected, so that they can, for example, understand and coherently organize simple speeches, interact with other people and, finally, express, in writing and orally, abstract and concrete ideas. To facilitate the selection in question, Reimann (2022) mentions 4 institutions²⁸ in Germany that offer language teaching at basic, intermediate and advanced levels, namely: Geschwister-Scholl-Gymnasium in Stuttgart-Sillenbuch, where Portuguese is learned from the 8th grade; the European School of Cologne (Europaschule Köln), which offers the language as an elective subject; the Max-Planck-Gymnasium in Dortmund, an institution whose objective is to integrate Portuguese-speaking students into the German educational system; and, finally, the European School, which is public and located in Berlin (Staatliche Europaschule Berlin, SESB), where Portuguese is taught not only as an additional language, but also as a mother tongue.

Based on the considerations in the preceding paragraphs, it is important to underline that, although the didactic sequence involves the interaction of students from a BS with students from a TS and a GS, it can also be implemented not only with students from schools in other countries where Portuguese is an official language, for example, Angola, Portugal, Equatorial Guinea, Cape Verde and Mozambique, but also with students from other countries where Portuguese is taught as an additional language, including Argentina and the United States.

4.2 Duration, content and objectives

- Duration – Fifteen forty-five-minute classes.
- Content – Elements, structure, characteristics and the 5 skills²⁹ of the ENEM textual genre; issues related to the current world, including immigration, poverty, environmental pollution and racial discrimination; linguistic and cultural aspects of East Timor and Germany.
- Objectives – To understand the objectives, structure and constituent elements of the ENEM essay; position oneself critically regarding current social issues; to develop interaction skills with

²⁸ In fact, the BS teacher can select, as a suggestion, one of these institutions.

²⁹ These skills will be mentioned later.

Portuguese speakers from other countries; learn about linguistic and cultural aspects of East Timor and Germany.

4.3 Development

4.3.1 Explanation of the objectives of the activities involving the ENEM textual genre – 1st to 3rd classes

First, the teacher explains to the BS students that, over the following weeks, they will participate in activities whose objective is to prepare them theoretically and methodologically for the textual genre required by ENEM. Such activities also involve virtual interaction with students from a TS and a GS and the creation of digital stories.

Since this is the first week, the teacher can address aspects related to the country, the city and the school of the Timorese and German students with whom they will interact. For instance, it is possible to suggest to the BS students, who will be sitting in pairs, that they search the Internet for magazines or books on linguistic and cultural references of Timor-Leste and Germany, e.g. climate, capital, characteristics of the Portuguese taught and spoken in these countries, population and system of government. Afterwards, the teacher can invite them to share what they have learned and, in addition, s/he can refer to the school of the Timorese and German students by showing images and videos.

4.3.2 Elements, characteristics and the 5 skills concerning the ENEM textual genre – 4th and 5th classes

At first, the teacher asks the students to form pairs, encouraging them to use the knowledge they already have about the ENEM textual genre. He then asks them to write words and expressions on the board that reflect what they already know, while the teacher can supplement the students' contributions with other comments. Afterwards, the teacher explains the elements that make up such textual genre, for example, the argumentative text and its characteristics, the supporting texts, the social problem, the thesis or point of view, the topic sentence, the arguments, the argumentative strategies for developing their ideas, and the proposal for social intervention. S/he also discusses the structure of this genre, in brief: introduction, development and conclusion.

Finally, the teacher address the 5 competencies of the ENEM essay, which are: (1) to demonstrate mastery of the standard Portuguese language; (2) to understand the ENEM essay proposal and apply concepts from the various areas of knowledge to develop the topic; (3) to select, relate, organize and interpret information, facts, opinions and arguments in defense of a point of view; (4) to demonstrate knowledge of the linguistic mechanisms necessary for the construction of arguments; (5) to develop a proposal for a solution to the problem addressed, showing respect for human values and considering socio-cultural diversity.

4.3.3 Production of digital stories - 6th to 10th classes

It should be emphasized that the activities from the 6th to the 10th class were based on the seven elements and steps of the digital story creation process according to Lambert (2006, 2007), as seen in the section that presented the theoretical framework. Furthermore, the teacher makes it clear that the script for the production of these stories, which will be described below, is in line with the content studied in the two previous classes.

First, s/he explains that, in these classes, the students will work in pairs, with each pair creating a digital story about a specific theme. It is important to note that the themes that will be covered — environmental pollution; racial discrimination; environmental sustainability; wars and conflicts between peoples; gender and sexuality discrimination; politics and ideologies; violence; climate change; exploitation of child labor; unequal distribution of wealth; hunger; immigration; water shortages; marginalized communities; poverty; terrorism; religion — could, directly or indirectly, be addressed in the ENEM exam of future years. As a suggestion, each pair will be assigned one of the mentioned themes by drawing lots.

Subsequently, the teacher will direct students to the website *educational uses of digital storytelling*³⁰. The website in question, in addition to containing numerous examples of digital stories already created, includes suggestions of resources that students can use in the process of producing their stories, such as software, materials and explanatory videos. Taking advantage of the opportunity, the teacher can present two videos available on YouTube — *what is digital*

³⁰ Link to access the website: <https://digitalstorytelling.coe.uh.edu/index.cfm>

storytelling?³¹ and *create a digital story*³² — which deal, in an objective and concise manner, with definitions of digital stories and how to create them.

On the basis of the structure of the ENEM textual genre, as well as the elements that compose it, the teacher suggests that students do the following for the script writing purposes: (1) briefly introduce themselves³³ (regarding both students from each pair), for example, name, where they live, profession, where they study, hobbies, etc.; (2) prepare a general introduction of the chosen theme; (3) present a social problem and a thesis related to the theme; (4) research sources, quotes, explanations, data, statistics, among other possibilities, for the purpose of substantiating the script's argumentative line of thought; (5) prepare a proposal for social intervention to solve/mitigate the mentioned problem, adding: (a) the proposal and how the problem could be solved/mitigated; (b) the agent (institution, agency, organization, etc.) responsible for its implementation; (c) the means, that is, the way in which the proposal will be put into practice; and (d) the resulting effect of the proposal, as well as additional information or detail. It should be noted that it is important for students to approach aspects linked to both the local, regional and global scope around the explored theme in the script.

Once the script writing process is complete, storyboards will be created to help the students visualize the “blueprint” in advance, namely the construction planning regarding their videos. In view of this, they will see this step as an “a priori/anticipated visualization” of the final result concerning the digital story, that is, the digitized video, ready. To do this, they can draw the storyboards with a pencil (an interesting and more traditional method), or look for websites/applications, i.e. *makeStoryboard*³⁴.

Soon after, the students will digitize the stories, in which they will include various digital resources, such as photos, background music, images, soundtrack, among others. In other words, they will narrate (with their own voice) the story, i.e. they will literally read and record the text of the script as the video progresses, and to this they will add, as already mentioned, different digital resources.

4.3.4 Presentation of the digital stories in a virtual exchange session – 11th and 12th classes

³¹ Link to access the website: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jlix-yVzheM&feature=youtu.be>

³² Link to access the website: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LVKeO5IIR_A&t=9s

³³ The importance of personal presentation in the videos is due to the fact that the BS, the TS and the GS students do not know each other beforehand.

³⁴ Link to access this storyboard creator: <https://makestoryboard.com/>

Each BS pair will have the chance to present their digital story not only to their classmates, but also via Skype, Zoom or Google Meet, to the TS and the GS students.

After the presentation of all the digital stories, there will be a proposal for dialogue, conducted in Portuguese, between the BS students and the TS and the GS students. As an illustration, the TS and the GS students, guided by the teacher from each school, can ask the BS students the following questions: 1) *did you enjoy participating in the production of the digital stories?*; 2) *in your opinion, did the process of creating the videos help you develop writing skills in Portuguese, as well as learn about the characteristics of the argumentative text?*; 3) *to what extent do you consider that this activity contributed to your familiarization with the structure of the ENEM essay?*; 4) *what did you learn from the topic you talked about?*.

4.3.5 Analysis of the ENEM essay grade 1000 – 13th and 14th classes

Each pair from the BS will receive the supporting text for the 2012 ENEM essay³⁵, whose theme was “the immigration movement to Brazil in the 21st Century”, and an example of a 1000 grade essay, i.e. from an ENEM candidate who scored 1000 that year³⁶. The students will read it and then, by means of an analysis exercise, will be responsible for: (1) discussing the pair's general impressions regarding the structural organization of the text and characteristics of the argumentative text; (2) identifying the problem; (3) identifying the thesis / point of view presented; (4) identifying the topic sentence in each of the paragraphs; (5) explaining which arguments, as well as strategies for developing these arguments, were used in defense of the thesis; (6) identifying the proposed social intervention, the agent, the means and the effect.

Later, again in a virtual exchange session, the BS teacher will explain to the TS and the GS students that the BS students carried out an activity of analyzing written texts based on the

³⁵ In this article, I selected the 2012 ENEM essay topic because, in addition to being directly related to one of the objectives of this study, which is to promote education for Global Citizenship, it continues to reflect the current reality in Brazil and other parts of the world. This means that the topic at stake, directly or indirectly, could be addressed again, in the future, in the ENEM exam. However, if the teacher prefers, it is possible to select a more recent topic, for example, the one addressed in 2023 (Challenges for tackling the invisibility of care work performed by women in Brazil), or in 2022 (Challenges for valuing traditional communities and peoples in Brazil).

³⁶ Examples of “essay grade 1000”, as well as supporting texts, can be found on the following page: <https://www.imaginie.com.br/enem/temas-de-redacao/enem-2012-o-movimento-imigratorio-para-o-brasil-no-seculo-xxi>

theme of immigration in Brazil in the 21st century. In this session, the BS students will put forward their analyses to the TS and the GS students.

To complete this step, a discussion will be proposed between the students of the BS and the TS and the GS students, raised by the following questions: (1) *considering that “the immigration movement to Brazil in the 21st Century” was the theme in the ENEM exam in 2012, do you believe that the topic “immigration in Brazil” continues to be relevant in the current year? Why?;* (2) *what social implications emerge from the expansion of current immigration not only in Brazil, but also in other countries?;* (3) *in the same way that Brazil welcomes immigrants and refugees, are there other countries that do the same, including East Timor and Germany? Explain;* (4) *which countries are known for welcoming Brazilian, Timorese and German immigrants?;* (5) *what are the challenges resulting from immigration in East Timor and Germany?.*

4.3.6 Completion of the activities involving the ENEM textual genre – 15th class

To conclude the activities, the BS students will write a text in class including their opinions and impressions regarding their participation in the aforementioned activities. The text can be built on the following questions: (1) *did you enjoy participating in the project activities? Why?;* (2) *do you think the activities helped you become familiar with the characteristics, structures and elements related to writing the ENEM essay?;* (3) *what is your opinion about the opportunity to interact with students from East Timor and Germany?;* (4) *how would you describe the students from the TS and the GS?;* (5) *what do you have to say about the way students from East Timor and Germany express themselves in Portuguese?;* (6) *what cultural and linguistic aspects (of Portuguese) did you notice when interacting with the students from the TS and the GS?;* (7) *what did you learn from the topic of immigration?;* (8) *what did you learn from each topic addressed in the digital stories?.*

After the teacher has read the text written by the BS students, s/he can prepare information material to mention in class the most salient aspects resulting from this reading. In addition, the teacher can discuss specific characteristics of Timorese Portuguese, including pronunciation and syntactic organization, and propose an exercise through which the BS students compare different dialects and registers as far as Timorese and Brazilian Portuguese is concerned.

Last but not least, the teacher can provide an opportunity for their students to reflect upon possible topics that could be covered in the ENEM exam in the current year, with the students mentioning these topics and explaining why this is possible. S/he can also suggest online platforms, such as

*Descomplica*³⁷ and *Corrija-me*³⁸, for students to prepare for their ENEM essays. These platforms even offer ENEM essay correction services.

Closing remarks

In favor of Global Citizenship education, Hanna (2024) proposes that teachers set aside time in class to discuss local, regional and global issues, apply activities aimed at developing students' critical thinking, encourage them to come up with proposals for solutions to problems that affect humanity and, finally, emphasize the importance of respecting cultural diversity. In line with Hanna's (2024) propositions, this study aimed to present a didactic sequence for the ENEM textual genre and, based on this sequence, to promote education for Global Citizenship within the internationalization context.

The didactic sequence presented can be applied over the course of 15 lessons. In summary, the teacher makes clear that the BS students will take part in activities designed to familiarize them with the ENEM textual genre, through which they will also be able to interact with the TS and the GS students. After explaining the elements, characteristics and 5 competences of this genre, the students will create digital stories on different themes, i.e. child labor exploitation, violence and climate change. After presenting the stories in a virtual exchange session for the TS and the GS students, the BS students will analyze the essays of candidates who, in 2012, scored 1000 in the ENEM exam. This analysis will again be presented to the TS and the GS students in a virtual exchange session. Lastly, the BS students will write a text reflecting on their experience of the activities that were conducted.

Belli and Luna (2024) and Hanna (2024) recommend that educational institutions should not only prepare students for the acquisition of academic knowledge, but also, through the internationalization of their activities, foster encounters between students from different cultures. In view of this, it is important to highlight that, in this study, the concept of internationalization transcended the perspective of spreading knowledge of the Portuguese language in different countries and continents. In other words, the activities that make up the didactic sequence are designed to enable the development of Global Citizenship through situations that stimulate critical thinking. Thus, in the context of teaching and learning Portuguese, didactic sequences that

³⁷ Link to access the website: <https://descomplica.com.br/d/vs/redacao/>

³⁸ Link to access the website: <https://www.corrijame.com.br/>

integrate virtual exchange and the production of digital stories, such as the didactic sequence suggested in this paper, can promote the discussion of themes related to contemporary societies, namely inclusion, ethnic-racial differences, gender and sexuality, discrimination and manifestations of prejudice. Such discussion, consequently, has the potential to favor Global Citizenship education.

In short, Guimarães and Silva (2022) stress that, in the context of internationalization, languages play a central role, seeing that social relations take place by means of language practices. In this regard, the authors go on to say that the lack of in-depth linguistic knowledge and proficiency in additional languages is one of the obstacles to the development of internationalization processes. From this perspective, it can be said that future didactic sequences that deal with the ENEM textual genre, such as the didactic sequence that was suggested in this study, can facilitate, in addition to linguistic and cultural knowledge itself, critical thinking in Brazilian schools —, and in other countries where Portuguese is spoken as an official language —, and the internationalization of the Portuguese language.

CRedit

Acknowledgement: I would like to thank the Alexander Humboldt Foundation (Germany) and CAPES (Brazil) for granting me a postdoctoral scholarship at the Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany.

Financing: This study is the result of my postdoctoral research, through Public Edict N. 14/2022, funded by the Alexander Humboldt Foundation (Germany) and CAPES (Brazil). Process number 88881.800200/2022-01.

Conflicts of interest: The authors certify that they have no commercial or associative interest that represents a conflict of interest in relation to the manuscript.

Ethical Approval: Not applicable.

Contributor Roles:

I herewith declare that I was solely responsible for the entire conceptualization of the study, for example, for reading and writing the theoretical basis, for developing the methodology corresponding to the didactic sequence and for writing and reviewing the article. SCHAEFER, Rodrigo.

References

- BECKER, J. *O Ensino do Português como Língua Estrangeira na Alemanha: enquadramento do Português no Ensino Superior Alemão*. 2015. 57 f. Dissertação (Mestrado em Ensino do Português como Língua Segunda e Estrangeira) — Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Lisboa, 2015. Available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10362/15731>. Accessed: 15 Mar. 2024
- BELLI, M.; LUNA, J. M. F. Uma teoria fundamentada sobre a atuação docente no contexto da educação global. In: LUNA, J. M. F.; SEQUEIRA, R. M. (Orgs.). *Currículo Escolar: Globalização e Perspetivas*. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2024. p. 9–26.
- CABRAL, N. F. *Sequências didáticas: estrutura e elaboração*. Belém: SBEM / SBEM-PA, 2017.

- CAPARROS JUNIOR, J. B. *Institucionalização da internacionalização da educação superior: estudo de aplicação prática à luz do círculo de internacionalização de Knight de 1994*. 2020. 128 f. Dissertação (Mestrado Profissional em Educação e Novas Tecnologias) — Centro Universitário Internacional UNINTER, Curitiba, 2020. Available at: <https://repositorio.uninter.com/handle/1/467>. Accessed: 10 Mar. 2024
- CASTAÑEDA, M. E. “I am proud that I did it and it’s a piece of me”: Digital Storytelling in the Foreign Language Classroom. *Calico Journal*, Ohio, v. 1, n. 30, p. 44-62, 2013. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/calicojournal.30.1.44>. Accessed: 06 Feb. 2024
- CAVALCANTE, F. M. L.; SILVA, A. A. O gênero redação do ENEM: um estado do conhecimento. *Revista Eletrônica de Estudos Integrados em Discurso e Argumentação*, Ilhéus, v. 23, n. 2, p. 51-70, 2023. DOI: 10.47369/eidea-23-2-3645. Available at: <https://periodicos.uesc.br/index.php/eidea/article/view/3645>. Accessed: 05 Apr. 2024
- CLIFFORD, V. Exploring internationalization of the curriculum through the lens of global citizenship. In: LUNA, J. M. F. (Org.). *Internacionalização do Currículo: Educação, Interculturalidade, Cidadania*. Campinas: Pontes, 2018. p. 13–31.
- COSTA-HÜBES, T. C.; SIMIONI, C. A. Sequência didática: uma proposta metodológica curricular de trabalho com os gêneros discursivos/textuais. In: BARROS, E.M. D.; RIOS-REGISTRO, E. S. (Orgs.). *Experiências em Sequências Didáticas de Gêneros Textuais*. Campinas, São Paulo: Pontes Editores, 2014. p. 15-39.
- GUIMARÃES, R. M.; SILVA, K. A. Políticas linguísticas para a internacionalização da educação: Um olhar decolonial a partir dos Institutos Federais. *Revista Linguagem em Foco*, Fortaleza, v. 14, n. 1, p. 33-56, 2022. DOI: 10.46230/2674-8266-14-8529. Available at: <https://revistas.uece.br/index.php/linguagememfoco/article/view/8529>. Accessed: 20 Jan. 2024
- HANNA, V. L. H. As humanidades, o pensamento crítico, a interculturalidade: Em busca de cidadãos globais. In: LUNA, J. M. F.; SEQUEIRA, R. M. (Orgs.). *Currículo Escolar: Globalização e Perspetivas*. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2024. p. 73–98.
- HUDZIK, J. K. *Comprehensive internationalization: from concept to action*. 1. ed. Washington: NAFSA, 2011.
- KÖHLER, F.; BRITZ, L.; MOROSINI, C. M. A internacionalização na Educação Básica e os marcos regulatórios nacionais. *Revista Humanidades & Inovação*, Palmas, v. 10, n. 11, p. 270-279, 2023. Available at: <https://revista.unitins.br/index.php/humanidadeseinovacao/article/view/9191>. Accessed: 20 Feb. 2024
- LAMBERT, J. *Digital storytelling: capturing lives, creating community*. 1. ed. Berkley: Digital Diner Press, 2006.
- LAMBERT, J. *Digital storytelling cookbook*. 1. ed. San Francisco: Digital Diner Press, 2007.
- LEASK, B. *Internationalizing the curriculum*. 1. ed. New York: Routledge, 2015.
- LEIRIA, I. Orientações Programáticas de Português Língua Não Materna (PLNM) - Ensino Secundário. Dili: Ministério da Educação/Direcção-Geral de Inovação e Desenvolvimento Curricular (DGIDC), 2010.
- MESQUITA, A. C. A promoção da língua portuguesa à escala global através do ensino do português como língua estrangeira. In: LUNA, J. M. F.; SEQUEIRA, R. M. (Orgs.). *Currículo*

Escolar: Globalização e Perspetivas. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2024. p. 123–138.

MIGUEL, A. J. Das políticas às práticas: possibilidades da noção de português língua pluricêntrica em formação de professores. In: KUHN, T. Z.; SCHOFFEN, J. R.; PERNA, C. B. L.; ANTUNES, A. J.; CARILLO, M. S. (Orgs.). *Português língua pluricêntrica: das políticas às práticas*. Campinas: Pontes Editores, 2022. p. 41–59.

NATIONAL STANDARDS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION PROJECT. *Standards for Foreign Language Learning: Preparing for the 21st Century* (SFFLL). Lawrence, KS: Allen Press, 1996.

NUNES, R. H.; SILVA, K. A. Ensino de língua portuguesa e educação humanizadora: protagonismo linguístico e emancipatório em tempo de crise. *Pesquisa e Ensino*, Barreiras, v. 1, n. 1, p. 166-188, 2022. DOI: 10.53282/pqe.v1i1.947. Available at: <https://revistas.ufob.edu.br/index.php/pqe/article/view/947>. Accessed: 03 May. 2024

O'DOWD, R. A transnational model of virtual exchange for global citizenship education. *Language Teaching*, Cambridge, v. 53, n. 4, p. 1-14, 2019. DOI: 10.1017/S0261444819000077. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/language-teaching/article/abs/transnational-model-of-virtual-exchange-for-global-citizenship-education/3C9CCB2AA8B68BB77EB2F42778D68619>. Accessed: 17 Apr. 2024

Accessed: 17 Apr. 2024

O'DOWD, R. Issues of equity and inclusion in Virtual Exchange. *Language Teaching*, Cambridge, p. 1-13, 2023a. DOI: 10.1017/S026144482300040X. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/language-teaching/article/issues-of-equity-and-inclusion-in-virtual-exchange/C983C00446286CC5CB2E60223F8B5527>. Accessed: 09 May. 2024

O'DOWD, R. Developing transferable skills in virtual exchange. *Journal of Virtual Exchange*, Groningen, v. 6, p. v-xii, 2023b. DOI: 10.21827/jve.6.41362. Available at: <https://journal.unicollaboration.org/article/view/41362>. Accessed: 07 Apr. 2024

REIMANN, D. Por quê uma didática do Português como língua estrangeira? (“Fachdidaktik Portugiesisch”) na Alemanha?: para a fundação de uma disciplina. In: COELHO, L. (Org.). *Portugal – Alemanha: convergências e divergências*. Portela: Lisbon International Press, 2022. p. 257–283.

ROBIN, B. R. The power of digital storytelling to support teaching and learning. *Digital Education Review*, Barcelona, v. 30, p. 17-29, 2016. DOI: 10.1344/der.2016.30.17-29. Available at: <https://revistes.ub.edu/index.php/der/article/view/16104>. Accessed: 20 June 2023

RODGERS, O.; NÍ DHONNCHADHA, L. The DNA of Digital Storytelling: a Case Study from a Higher Education LSP Classroom. *The EuroCALL Review*, Valencia, v. 30, n. 1, p. 63-77, 2023. DOI: 10.4995/eurocall.2023.17232. Available at: <https://polipapers.upv.es/index.php/eurocall/article/view/17232>. Accessed: 09 Apr. 2024

SCHAEFER, R. Digital storytelling in the internationalization context: towards English learning. *Todas as Letras*, São Paulo, v. 24, n. 2, p. 1-19, 2022. Available at: <http://editorarevistas.mackenzie.br/index.php/tl/article/view/14857>. Accessed: 05 July 2024

SCHAEFER, R.; HEEMANN, C. Telecolaboração: Pela cidadania global na internacionalização do currículo em uma instituição de ensino brasileira. In: LUNA, J. M. F.; SEQUEIRA, R. M. (Orgs.). *Currículo Escolar: Globalização e Perspetivas*. Coimbra: Imprensa da Universidade de Coimbra, 2024. p. 99–122.

SCHAEFER, R.; HEEMANN, C; BELLI, M. O papel da telecolaboração na mobilidade acadêmica. In: LUNA, J. M. F.; SEHNEM, P.R. *O Programa Ciências sem Fronteiras em Avaliação*. São Paulo: Pontes Editores, 2017. p. 231-248.

SEVERO, C. G.; LEVISKI, C. E. Internacionalização da língua portuguesa: assimetrias, heterogeneidade e poder. *Organon*, Porto Alegre, v. 34, p. 1-16, 2019. DOI: 10.22456/2238-8915.90747. Available at: <https://seer.ufrgs.br/organon/article/view/90747>. Accessed: 16 May 2024

TIMOR-LESTE. Decreto-Lei n. 47/2011, de 18 de outubro de 2011. Plano Curricular do Ensino Secundário Geral do Ministério da Educação de Timor-Leste. Jornal da República Democrática de Timor-Leste, Governo de Timor-Leste, Timor-Leste, 2011.

UNESCO. *Global Citizenship Education: Topics and Learning Objectives*. Paris: UNESCO, 2015. Available at: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0023/002329/232993e.pdf>

ZABALA, A. *A prática educativa: como ensinar*. 1. ed. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 1998.